

COMPARATIVE RESEARCH OF MODIFICATIONS OF VERBS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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***Abstract.** The study of the development of national languages in the 21st century has become one of the important issues in cognitive directions in determining the development of national languages. For the artistic world, which can be understood in the field of art, in a national cultivated world in the field, the practical phase of the thinking of speaking and imagining specific tongues will be consistent.*

***Keywords:** movement, verb, language, translation, method, result.*

СРАВНИТЕЛЬНОЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ МОДИФИКАЦИЙ ГЛАГОЛОВ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ

***Аннотация.** Изучение развития национальных языков в XXI веке стало одним из важных вопросов в познавательных направлениях в определении развития национальных языков. Для художественного мира, который может быть понят в поле искусства, в национальном культурном мире в поле будет последовательной практической фазой мышления говорения и воображения на конкретных языках.*

***Ключевые слова:** движение, глагол, язык, перевод, способ, результат.*

INTRODUCTION

Scientific areas of the study of the modification process in the field of artistic dots are consistently implemented to analyze the use of the modification process during the dialogue and the lingational methods of communication during communication and linguates communicative purposes. As a result, the scope of scientific directions concerning the description of the backup capabilities of individual levels of different languages is expanding.

However, most of the research is typical of one language obtained separately, and therefore there is a need to study the circumstances of the movement modifiers on the basis of comparative analysis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The issue of the general issues of movement modifiers in English linguistics, the issue of various and express means were studied in the research of G.Pocheptsov, L.S.Arheeva, S.I.Guzeeva, Jousy, Jousyn, J. Tosinin, J.Mey, R.Jackendro, Nabils, Chuckice, Dj.layonz, and other scientists.

In Russian linguistics V.V.Burlaxova, T.I.Ivanova, A.A.kobrina, V.A.Korneva, N.D.An.Korutyunova, s. Katsnelson, I.M.Kobozeva, N.N.BoldyRev was studied by E.N.Kotelova, V.A.Maslova and and others worked on it.

Among uzbek linguistics M.Umarkhodjaev, A.Khrasulov, I.Rakhamarov, Sh.S.Rakharov, A.Rasdurahmonov, Sh.S. Safarov, M. Nurmanov, M. Nurmanov, N.Mahmudov, A.e.Mamatov, S.Mukhamedova, R. Sayfullaeva and others gave their opinions on this issue.

RESULTS

More interesting and significant differences in the matter of transitivity and intransitivity of the verbs between English and Uzbek are in the plan of content. So, some transitive English verbs have intransitive verb correspondences in Uzbek comp.:

to follow (smb., smth.)- *ergashmoq*
 to approach (smb., smth.)- *yaqinlashmoq*
 to watch (smb., smth.)- *kuzatmoq*
 and vice versa :
 to listen to (smb., smth.) - *tinglamoq*
 to wait for (smb., smth.) - *kutmoq*

It is obvious, that the possibility of two-fold “solution” of any action (either as transitive or as intransitive) is put in the fact of the connection of the verb with two poles: the bearer of the action and its object. Therefore there cannot be absolute border between transitive and intransitive verbs. Thus the verb to watch can be translated not only as ‘*kuzatmoq*’, but also as ‘*tomosha qilmoq*’.

In order to understand why English, usually striving for formal completeness and logical exactness of expressing, in this case it is going along contrary way, we must remember the aspiration of Englishmen to compensate syntactical constraint of their speech with more freedom in morphological and semantic relations. It is obvious, that the rubbing off the borders between transitive and intransitive verbs is one those compensating means, which expand and enrich the opportunities of the language. As a result the broadening of the meaning of many verbs occurs. Here we can also observe the influence of grammatical structure of the language on the character of its lexicon. For example:

She laughed unwillingly, and the laughing reflection under the green hat decided her instantly. U hohlamagan holda kulib yubordi, uning yashil shlyapasi ostidagi kulayotgan chehrasining oynadagi aksi uni qaror chiqarishiga majbur qildi.

You don't know what a life she led me. – *Sizlar uni mening hayotimni do'zzahga aylantirganini bilmaysizlar.*

DISCUSSION

One of the possible reasons is that phrasal verbs have not been amply placed within the curriculum of many educational institutes and the absence of translation teaching materials to familiarize English language learners and translators with specific constructions; therefore, the frequency of phrasal verbs within the translation must be reviewed and revised accordingly to reduce the problems of translating phrasal verbs for translators, especially for those who are translating them from English to Uzbek. Conducting further research on this ground will undoubtedly help us to overcome some hurdles of this kind. Another problem of phrasal verb translation which requires further research is a semantic feature of them because the possibility of preserving the polysemous meaning of English phrasal verbs while they are being translated into Uzbek is another rare case. The present study has also explored the effect of context in translating phrasal verbs into Uzbek of English, and we could suggest that the use of sentence context was better in achieving retention than using the translation condition. This does not mean that the use of context is always better than the translation condition, but context is more beneficial when retaining vocabulary knowledge. However, the effect of the learning conditions was closely related to the other factors such as the proficiency level, first language, and the combination of the learning.

CONCLUSIONS

The prospect for the future would be better, if we are aware of the fact that becoming much familiar with all peculiarities of phrasal verbs can be the most effective tool in learning as

well as the translation of them. It is a common phenomenon and undisputable fact that high accuracy in the acquisition of phrasal verbs and treatment of phrasal verbs in practical translation can prevent most translators and learners from hardships and disgrace in the translation. The present analysis will hopefully contribute to the studies of language transfer and in particular of transfer issues in the usage of English phrasal verbs.

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